

Implementation of the Model of Integrated Care for People with Type 2 Diabetes in two Community Health Organizations

Interviewer Administered Questionnaire

Aim:

- 1) To inform service design to ensure it meets the needs of general practice
- 2) To provide a baseline against which we can measure change

Practice: _____

Completed by: _____ (GP/ PN/ Practice Manager) **on behalf of the Practice.**

1.0 PRACTICE DEMOGRAPHICS

1.1 How many of the following staff are working in the practice?

Please enter as WTE's (e.g. half time staff = 0.5 WTE)

	WTEs
GP's	
GP Registrar	
Practice Nurses*	
Practice Manager	
Other Administrative Staff	

*1.1.1 If any of the Practice Nurses are CNS, ANP or Nurse prescribers, please provide details: _____

1.2 What is the total practice patient population?

(E= Estimated; A= Actual)

	No.	E/A
Overall		
GMS/GPVC patients		
Non GMS (private) patients*		

(*we understand the limitations in accurately identifying number of private patients: we suggest all private patients who have attended your practice in past 3y)

1.3 How many patients have a confirmed diagnosis of the following?

Enter **A** for actual number e.g from your register/disease coding

Enter **E** for estimated number if you don't have a register

	No.	E/A
Type 2 Diabetes		
T2D - GMS/GPVC		
T2D - Private (non GMS)		
Type 1 Diabetes		
Other e.g. MODY		

1.4 Has this practice a diabetes register?

Yes	
No	

1.4.1 If yes, describe format e.g. excel/ other? _____

1.4.2 If yes, who updates the register/adds new patients to the register? _____

1.5 Does this practice code people with diabetes (e.g. disease coding)?

Yes	
No	

1.6 Which of the following is the register used for?

(Please tick all that apply)

Calculating the number of patients with diabetes in the practice	
Call/ recall purposes for Diabetes Cycle of Care / CDM	
programme Auditing and feedback to monitor the quality of	
diabetes care Other	

If other, please specify: _____

1.7 Which practice management IT system does the practice use?

Health One	
Helix Practice Manager	
Socrates	
Complete GP	
None. We use paper records.	

1.8 Is this practice registered to deliver the Chronic Disease Management Programme?

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

1.9 Is this practice practice registered to deliver the Diabetes Cycle of Care?

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.0 STRUCTURED DIABETES CARE FOR TYPE 2 DIABETES

2.1 Has this practice practice previously availed of the services of the CNS Diabetes Integrated Care?

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.2 How has Covid-19 affected the ability of this practice to deliver structured routine diabetes reviews?

We temporarily paused undertaking routine diabetes reviews	<input type="checkbox"/>
We continue to undertake <i>mostly</i> face-to-face routine diabetes reviews	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.2.1 If you continue to undertake routine diabetes reviews please tick one box which best describes how you currently deliver reviews diabetes reviews

We have changed to mostly telephone / virtual consultations	<input type="checkbox"/>
We provide a mix of both F2F & virtual/telephone	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.3 Does the practice use a recall system for scheduling diabetes review visits? (A recall system might be formal, or more informal such as linking recall to blood tests/prescription requests etc)

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.3.1 If yes, please tick which patient groups you recall?

All patients with Type 2 Diabetes (GMS & Private patients)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Only diabetes patients with a GMS / GPVC Card	<input type="checkbox"/>
We only recall patients who have uncontrolled/complicated diabetes	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.4 In general, how often do you routinely perform diabetes review appointments for patients with stable /uncomplicated type 2 diabetes)?

Comment: _____

Opportunistic review	<input type="checkbox"/>
Annually	<input type="checkbox"/>
Twice a year	<input type="checkbox"/>
Three or more times a year	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.5 If you are referring a patient to the specialist diabetes service, which hospital does your practice usually refer to?

[Include hospital list here]

2.5.1 If other, please specify: _____

2.6 Are there any aspects of Type 2 Diabetes care which you consider more challenging/unsafe to provide during the Covid 19 pandemic?

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.6.1 If yes, please provide details: _____

3.0 ACCESS TO DIETETIC SERVICE

3.1 Do you have access to a HSE Dietetic Service?

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

3.1.1 If no, do you refer patients to a private dietitian?

Yes	
No	

3.2 If you have access to a dietetic service, who to you usually refer? _____

3.3 Do you have the following resources in the practice

Height measure	
Measuring tape for waist circumference	
Diabetes & Diet leaflets/online resources	

3.4 Before the Covid-19 pandemic did you refer patients with newly diagnosed Type 2 Diabetes to a group-based Structured Diabetes Education Programme?

Always	
Usually	
Never	
Not available locally	

3.3.1 If yes, which programme you refer to? (Please tick all that apply)

Discover Diabetes	
DESMOND	
CODE	

3.3.2 If you don't refer, please clarify why: _____

4.0 FOOT CARE AND PODIATRY ACCESS

4.1 Do you have access to a HSE Podiatry Service?

Yes	
No	

4.1.1 If no, do you refer patients to a private podiatrist?

Yes	
No	

4.2 If you have access to a Podiatry service, who do you usually refer? _____

4.3 Do you have access to the following foot screening resource in the practice?

10g Monofilament	
128 Hz Tuning Fork	
Foot care leaflets	

4.4 Do you perform annual foot screening as part of the patients diabetes review?

Yes	
No	

4.4.1 If yes, who performs this assessment?

GP	
Practice Nurse	
Other	

4.4.2 If other, please specify: _____

4.3 Have staff in this practice been trained in diabetic foot screening?

Yes	
No	

If yes, provide details (staff members name, course, date): _____

Would further training in diabetic foot screening be useful?

Yes	
No	

5.0 ACCESS TO PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT

5.1 Has the practice access to a HSE Psychology/Counselling service?

Yes	
No	

If yes, please provide details: _____

6.0 DIABETES SUPPORT & CPD

6.1 Has any staff member completed a healthcare professional diabetes education programme?

Yes	
No	

6.1.1 If yes, please provide detail (staff members name, course, date) _____

6.2 Has your practice any specific education/training needs relating to diabetes care?

Yes	
No	

6.2.1 If yes, please provide details: _____

6.3 How useful would it be to have 'shadowing' opportunities for any of the practice staff with the CNS, Podiatrist or Dietitian? (i.e. observing a clinic)

Not particularly useful	
A little useful	
Moderately useful	
Very useful	

6.4 How useful would it be to have the network Diabetes Dietitian support the management of your diabetes patients in the community?

Not particularly useful	
A little useful	
Moderately useful	
Very useful	

6.4.1 If you wouldn't find this service useful, please explain: _____

6.5 How useful would it be to have the network Diabetes Podiatrist support the management of your diabetes patients in the community?

Not particularly useful	
A little useful	
Moderately useful	
Very useful	

6.5.1 If your practice wouldn't find this service useful, please explain: _____

6.6 How useful would it be to have the network Diabetes CNS support the management of your diabetes patients in the community?

Not particularly useful	
A little useful	
Moderately useful	
Very useful	

6.6.1 If your practice wouldn't find this service useful, please explain: _____

6.7 If this practice would find the support of a CNS Diabetes useful, please indicate your preferred method of support:

Usually (in non-covid times)	Run clinics within our practice for selected patients with complicated diabetes	
	OR	
	Review selected patients with complicated diabetes in the Primary Care Centre	
During the Covid 19 Pandemic	Deliver face-to-face / virtual / telephone consultations from our practice	
	OR	
	Deliver face-to-face /telephone /virtual consultations from the Primary Care Centre	

6.7 In what other way can the new Diabetes Integrated Care Team support this practice?

Please provide details: _____

6.8 Is there anything that you would like to add in relation to diabetes care at this practice?

Please provide details: _____

THANK YOU FOR TAKING THE TIME TO COMPLETE THIS QUESTIONNAIRE